

**STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE ADVERTISEMENT WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS.**

Dr. Krishna Kumar TP

Former Director, SNMV Institute of Management, Coimbatore

Abstract

The current exploration report accentuations on concentrating on the effect of web advertising on consumer buying behavior, which raises the consumers' expectations towards the item and buying behaviors. The buying behavior is firmly affected by the picture of the item which is worked by the promoters. Publicists are relied upon to move their concentration and burn through millions in web advertising before long than TV, print promotions and another conventional advertising media. Online shopping is a developing pattern in India and the quantities of the two merchants and purchasers are expanding day by day by walloping rates. India's complete online marketing projection is assessed to arrive at the US \$100 billion by 2020. With the fast development in innovation, the web is turning into a significant one stop point for consumers in viewing as the vast majority of their requirements. Be it communication, amusement, data search or shopping, web fills in as a panacea for every one of their necessities. As per the worldwide systems administration monster Cisco, Digital change will take India's web clients from 373 million (28 percent of populace) in 2016 to 829 million (59 percent of the Indian populace) in 2021. This plainly exhibits that India is developing quick and individuals are becoming routine of involving the Internet as the advancement of human culture, the improvement in Communication processes and Digital Convergence open up imaginative open doors and difficulties for Marketing. In this manner, the Internet has pushed forward to assume a huge part in the Consumer Decision Making Process. Numerous consumers are online consistently for their own and official work, yet do they notice the promotions, flags showed on that website page and most significant thing is to actually take a look at what is their review esteem. The current review examined the effect of web advertising on consumer buying behavior by directing an overview.

Key Words: Online Advertising, Marketing communication, Consumer behavior

INTRODUCTION

Online advertising, additionally called online marketing or Internet advertising or web advertising, is a type of marketing and advertising which utilizes the Internet to convey special marketing messages to consumers. The web has is a continuous arising source that will in general extend to an ever increasing extent and is filling dramatically in the two its applications and number of clients because of its interesting qualities of adaptability, intelligence, and personalization. Web as an advertising medium is adaptable and here it stands separated from the conventional advertising mode. It is an exceptionally adaptable mode that permits consumer to make shifts during the direction of the mission as and when expected without bringing about much extra expense. This makes web even more significant in a nation like India where the business situation is profoundly powerful and changes as time passes. Online marketing media permits the consumer to make changes as and when expected to satisfy the most recent needs of the market. The quantity of web clients is on a quick ascent worldwide and the web is being utilized by consumers of all age and types. Web has become one of the significant mechanism for communication, amusement and is for sure during the time spent supplanting conventional diversion, promotion items, and enlightening media's. In like manner, conventional marketing structures like TV, radio, paper, magazines, and so on, are turning into a relic of past times. The greater part of the organizations and associations these days are depending on advanced advertising and marketing

methods to work on their general deals and income. Online marketing has up to this point ended up being successful and proficient when contrasted and different types of advertising and marketing. It incorporates email marketing, web index marketing (SEM), online media marketing, many kinds of show advertising (counting web standard advertising), and versatile advertising. Like other advertising media, online advertising habitually includes both a distributor, who incorporates promotions into its online substance, and a sponsor, who gives the notices to be shown on the distributor's substance. Other potential members incorporate advertising organizations who help create and put the promotion duplicate, an advertisement server which innovatively conveys the advertisement and tracks insights, and advertising associates who accomplish autonomous special work for the publicist.

TYPES OF ONLINE ADVERTISEMENT

Online advertisement is comprehensively separated in to the accompanying sorts:

Show Advertising: the utilization of web standards or flag advertisements put on an outsider site to direct people to an organization's own site and increment item mindfulness.

Web search tool Marketing (SEM): a type of marketing that tries to advance sites by expanding their perceivability in web crawler result pages (SERPs) using either paid position, context oriented advertising, and paid incorporation, or using free site design improvement procedures.

Site improvement (SEO): the method involved with working on the perceivability of a site or a page in web indexes through the "normal" or un-paid ("natural" or "algorithmic") query items.

Video Ads: While YouTube advertisements are the most famous and notable of video promotions, there are really a few unique arrangements, types and content choices. Consumers can go the course of instructive/educational. Or on the other hand perhaps consumers need to present a how-on. Attempt to make on the passionate things happen of consumer watchers by making a visual story. Ideal for marking, particularly assuming you have an item or administration that is best shown outwardly.

Email Marketing: Hanging out with Display Ads back close to the beginning of online advertising, Email Marketing is a less expensive, quicker and powerful type of advertising. It's an extraordinary method for building client devotion and lift deals; when you utilize an email crusade director (see the rundown underneath) to plan and send your messages, you can without much of a stretch track how well they do and screen your ROI

Remarketing/Retargeting: The most ideal way to market to consumers who definitely have any familiarity with the current item and administration is to remarket to them. Whenever consumers visit online webpage, merchants drop a treat on them so that, as they travel around the web, online promotions will show up again and again to remind them regarding the vender's items or administrations.

LIMITATIONS OF ONLINE ADVERTISEMENT

Consumers Ignore Ads: Consumers are so used to seeing advertising on TV, hearing radio plugs and flipping through advertisements in magazines, they've fostered an antipathy for all types of advertising. This is additionally the situation with online advertising, where consumers can try not to click pennant advertisements, sidestep promotions in online recordings they watch and close spring up advertisements when they come up on their screens. Clients are in charge of which advertising messages they need to snap and react to.

Seeing Problems: Website personal time, slacks in site or video stacking and program inconveniences can lessen the times consumers see online advertisements and how well they see them. Whenever specialized issues happen, organizations lose the amazing chance to communicate advertisements for their items and benefits and may lose expected deals. Seeing issues can happen as a result of issues with a site or then again assuming that a consumer is utilizing a PDA or other cell phone to see a site, has a sluggish association speed or doesn't have the right applications and projects introduced on his PCs for

legitimate survey.

Consumers Get Distracted: When clients visit a site, they normally have an objective as a top priority, regardless of whether it's to make up for lost time with the most recent big name tattle, read the news, talk with companions, download music or shop for a particular thing. Sites present consumers with different choices that can without much of a stretch divert them and pull their consideration from your online advertisements.

One impediment of advertising on the Internet is that the marketing materials are consequently accessible for anybody on the planet to duplicate, no matter what the legitimate implications. Logos, pictures and brand names can be replicated and utilized for business purposes, or even to criticism or fake your organization. This isn't true with TV and magazine advertising, wherein pictures should be duplicated rather than just replicated electronically.

Another impediment is the way that the Internet-advertising dash for unheard of wealth has started to acquaint promotion mess with the Web. Web clients are so immersed with standard promotions and spam email that they have started to overlook web advertising similarly as much as advertisements on customary media.

Confounds the consumers: Many a period misshaped form of the truth is displayed in the advertising. Trusting in advertising, consumers purchase the item. On its utilization, they feel cheated. Consumers come to acknowledge later that the data given in the advertisement was something different while the real item was very not quite the same as it. Along these lines, individuals lose trust in advertising as a result of wrong show. In this reference it is said that advertising befuddles rather than makes a difference. Security Concerns: According to a US Senate examination, the present status of online advertising jeopardizes the security and protection of clients.

Security concerns: The assortment of client data by distributors and promoters has raised consumer worries regarding their protection. A little over half of Internet clients would utilize Do Not Track innovation to hinder all assortment of data whenever offered a chance. Over portion of all Google and Facebook clients are worried about their security while utilizing Google and Facebook, as indicated by Gallup.

The person who's most advantages from online advertisement are E-trade like Amazon, Myntra, Flipkart, Jabong and so on Internet business is encountering an unrivaled extension for north of 10 years. From a couple of percent a decade prior to practically 20% for specific classifications of items, the Internet has turned into a significant deals divert in the B2C globalized trade.

Particularly during the merry season e-posteriors are attempting to charm customers with best arrangements like EORS (End of Reason Sale) EOSS (End of Season Sale), BBD (Big Billion Day deal) and get piece of the pie. These organizations contributes vigorously on bringing the best arrangements for consumers across classes like clothing, hardware, and family things as well as on strategies to guarantee rapid conveyance to guarantee consumer experience doesn't endure.

While the person who misfortunes the most out of it are generally customary store venders. Assume I purchase a pristine book for Rs. 1000 on Amazon. Whenever I've gotten done with understanding it, I can likely sell it for at minimum Rs. 350-650 on any recycled site (like eBay, Craigslist or Priceminister). The entire interaction hurts double the customary book retailer. The initial occasion when I purchase the book through amazon.

The subsequent when I sell it as a second-hand. In doing as such, I have consumed the "activity of perusing" The Second-hand market is consistently expanding with the assistance of online advertisements through site and portable applications like OLX and so on Everybody is currently client and a provider.

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Muhammad Aqsa& Dwi Kartini (2015) observed that the constant advancement of innovation builds the web clients definitely. The web is worked by the contraptions like PC, Laptop, Mobile telephone, Tablets and so on so to catch the enormous strength of consumers' online advertising is exceptionally necessary. The investigation likewise discovered that albeit online advertising is viable however it must be designated to those main who utilized the web constantly.
- Harshini C.S (2015) observed that the web-based media is changing customs of individuals. Individuals are progressively utilizing online media to look for data rather than different media like TV, magazine, and radio. So the organizations need to make compelling online advertising systems since web is presently the best stage to catch enormous number of consumers. Subsequently, online advertisements assume a significant part in current situation.
- The way of thinking accepts that the web advertising makes the negative and positive discernment among the consumers. It is intriguing to concentrate on that where such a large amount research has been directed with respect to eventual fate of online advertising and the consumer behavior towards it. However individuals appreciate taking a gander at online advertisement, its development and utility for settling on behavioral buying choices likewise plays role.(Ann E.Schlosser, Sharon Shavitt& Alaina (1999).

♣ Automated and Tech-savvy market

E-advertising where advertisers delegate different assignments to the best hands and abilities, web marketing exploits educated technique.

Table-1: Respondents Profile

Question Number	Questions/Statements	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender of respondents		
	Male	27	27%
	Female	73	73%
Total		100	100%
2	Age of respondents		
	18-27	75	75%
	28-37	15	15%
	38-47	05	05%
	48-57	05	05%
Total		100	100%

Source: Field survey data

Table -1: Respondents Profile

Question Number	Questions / Statements	Number of respondents	Percentages
1	Gender of respondents		
	Male	27	27%
	Female	73	73%
Total		100	100%
2	Age of respondents		
	18-27	75	75%
	28-37	15	15%
	38-47	05	05%
	48-57	05	05%

Total		100	100%
--------------	--	------------	-------------

Out of those 100 respondents 75% were under the age gathering of 18 to 27, 15% were under the age gathering of 28 to 37, 5% were under the age gathering of 38 to 47 and remaining were under the age gathering of 48 to 57. The overview was directed on 100 individuals and among them the greater part of the respondent are females.

Table -2: Views of respondents on various kinds of E- advertisement

Serial Number	Online advertisements	Number of respondents
1	Social Media	65
2	Video advertisement	02
3	Display advertisement	11
4	SEW and SEO	19
5	Others	03
Total		100

Source: field survey

Table 2 demonstrates that out of 100 examples, 65 individuals like Social media advertisement, 2 individuals like video advertisement, 11 individuals like Display advertisement, 19 individuals like SEM and SEO and other 2 individuals like other sort of online advertising.

Table-3: Respondents attitude towards online advertisements

Likert 's Scale	Frequency
Like	45
Strongly like	03
Dislike	21
Strongly Dislike	02
Neutral	29
Total	100

Source : field survey data

Table 3 shows the disposition of the respondents towards e-advertisement. Out of 100 respondents 45 individuals preferences and 3 individuals unequivocally enjoys the e-advertisement, 21 individuals abhorrences and 2 individuals emphatically detests the e-advertisement and staying 29 are impartial.

Table -4: Influence of online advertisement on purchase

Question Number	Questions / Statements	Number of Respondents
1	Online advertisement influence on shopping trends	
	Yes	89
	No	11
Total		100
2	Respondents purchase decision after seeing online ads	
	Very Often	7
	Often	37
	Sometimes	31
	Rarely	24
	Never	1
Total		100

Source: field survey

Out of 100 examples, 89 respondents felt that online advertisements expanded their shopping patterns. 7 individuals settle on buy choice regularly subsequent to seeing online advertisements, 37 individuals Often settle on buy decision, 31 respondents settle on buy choice sometimes, 24 respondents settle on buy choice once in a blue moon and 1 respondent never makes any Table 4 expresses that, among 100 respondents 89 of them feel that the online advertisement has buy choice in the wake of seeing online advertisements

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

Table-5 : Chi-Square Analysis

Chi-Square Test	Table Value	Level of Significant
10.114	9.488	Highly Significant

Source: Field survey data

The Chi-Square investigation shows that the invalid theory, i.e., there is no connection between the online advertisement and consumer buying behavior is dismissed and the elective speculation is acknowledged. Accordingly we can reason that there is a connection between online advertisement and consumer buying behavior.

CONCLUSION

Web advertising offers expanded consciousness of organizations, a simple technique to disseminate data, progressed strategies for focusing on consumers, a quick and direct line to the consumers. Online advertisement enjoy dealers straight forwardly with designated consumers . The advertisement ought not be meddlesome and distractive in nature. Such advertisement ought to be inventive to draw in an ever increasing number of consumers. With the expanded reception promotion parting of the Internet, World Wide Web is turning out to be slowly a standard advertisement stage. The need is to comprehend the objective consumers and afterward plan shrewdly to acquire most extreme out of this new medium.

REFERENCES

1. Barbara k. Kaye and Norman Medoff. (2001) just a click away: advertising on the internet, Massachusetts: Allyn and Bacon.
2. Dreze, Xavier and Francois Hussherr, (2003) ‘internet advertising: is anybody watching’, Journal of interactive marketing, vol.17, no.4:8-23.
3. Gordon, M.E. & De Lima-Tumer, K. (1997). Consumers’ attitude towards Internet advertising. International Marketing Review, Vol.14 No.5, pp. 362-375.
4. Harridge S. March 2004 ‘Electronic marketing, the new kid on the block’, Marketing Intelligence & Planning, Vol.22, no.3, pp.297-309.
5. Upasana K, Kumar N, & Gupta A. (2015). A study of online purchase behaviour of consumers in India. ICTACT journal of Management Studies, 01(03), 136-142.
6. Graydon, Shari (2003) "Made You Look - How Advertising Works and Why You Should Know", Toronto: Annick Press, ISBN 1-55037-814-7 [3].
7. Johnson, J. Douglas, "Advertising Today", Chicago: Science Research Associates, 1978. ISBN 0-574- 19355-3
8. Gibson, Mathias (12 July 2012). "History of Online Display Advertising". Vantage Local. Retrieved 23 June 2013.
9. Kuester, Sabine (2012): MKT 301: Strategic Marketing & Marketing in Specific Industry Contexts, University of Mannheim, p. 110.
10. Lynn R. Kahle; Angeline G. Close (2011). Consumer Behavior Knowledge for Effective Sports and Event Marketing. New York: Routledge. ISBN 978-0-415-87358-1.
11. Elizabeth A. Minton; Lynn R. Khale (2014). Belief Systems, Religion, and Behavioral Economics. New York: Business Expert Press LLC. ISBN 978-1-60649-704-3.
12. J. Scott Armstrong (1991). "Prediction of Consumer Behavior by Experts and Novices" (PDF). Journal of Consumer Research. Journal of Consumer Research Inc. 18: 251–256. doi:10.1086/209257.
13. Sandhusen, Richard L.: Marketing (2000). Cf. S. 218
14. Trochim, W.M.K, (2006). Research Methods Knowledge Base.
15. Shields, Patricia and Rangarjan, N. 2013. A Playbook for Research Methods
16. End Model and Synthesis of Evidence”. The Journal of Marketing, Vol. 52, No. 3 (Jul., 1988), pp. 2-22

17. Bagirathiyer, An Analytical Study Of Impact Of Marketing Strategies Of Company In Developing Brand Name And Brand Acceptance Of Consumer Durable Goods With Special Reference To Nagpur Region(From The Dealers Perspective), International Journal Of Research In Business Management, Vol. 3, Issue 12, Dec 2015, 27-38
18. Yu-Jing Chiu, Hsiao-Chi Chen, Gwo-HshungTzeng, Joseph Z. Shyu (Institute of Management of Technology, National Chiao Tung University) “Marketing strategy based on customer behaviour for LCD T.V”. International Journal of management and decision, Vol. 7, No.2-3\2006 (Pgs. 143-165).
19. Larry J. Rosenberg, John A. Czepiel, (1984), “A Marketing Approach For Customer Retention", Journal of Consumer Marketing. Vol. 1 Iss: 2, pp.45 – 51
20. P.Kotler, G. Armstrong,” Customer driven Marketing Strategy,” in Principles of Marketing, 13th Edition. Pearson Education Inc.2010,pp 160 to 170
21. M.Irfan, C. Sumangala, L. D’ Souza,” Green Marketing Mix Strategies of Consumer Durables with reference to automobile sector”, International Journal Of Emerging Research in Management and Technology, ISSN: 2278 [18]. lume -3, Issue -6), June 2014.
22. P. Yannopolous, “Impact of the Internet on Marketing strategy formulation”, International Journal of Business & Social science, Vol.2 No.18; Oct 2011.
23. Nielson (2011) Nielson Global Online Consumer Confidence and Opinion Survey \$Q-2010, The Nielson & Co, USA
24. NMCC (2009) Assessment of the Comparative Advantage of Various Consumer Goods Produced in India Vis-à-Vis their Chinese Counterparts
25. Rama B (2010) Drunken Man’s Wald, Business Standard, February 20, New Delhi
26. Bettis RA, Hitt Ma (1995), The New Competitive Landscape. The Strategic Management Journal16:7- 19